

APPLICATION OF GEOSTATISTICS AND SELF-ORGANIZING MAPS FOR ESTIMATION OF GROUNDWATER LEVEL SPATIAL DISTRIBUTION IN COMPLEX HYDROGEOLOGICAL SYSTEMS

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Abstract

Water scarcity is a major global problem and expected to become even more significant in the near future. Overexploitation of groundwater, from direct and indirect activities, mainly due to intensive agricultural activity, combined with projected climatic change, has a great impact on the hydrological/hydrogeological conditions of the Mediterranean region. This generates concerns over the sustainability of groundwater resources.

In this work, a geostatistical analysis approach, in combination with a machine-learning algorithm, i.e. Self-Organizing Maps (SOM), was applied with three main goals. a) to develop reliable spatial maps of groundwater level variability in a large-scale hydrogeological system of complex aquifers, and to identify groundwater level zones, b) to process efficiently a large dataset of 2524 wells using geostatistical analysis and c) to accurately map groundwater level spatial distribution in a local scale. As a first step, the algorithm applied Self-Organizing Maps to identify locally similar input data, and then used those identified clusters of data, by means of Ordinary Kriging to estimate the spatial distribution of groundwater level and produce maps in large and local scales.

The proposed method provides a complementary tool to physically based models that require extensive data and hydrogeological details to produce reliable large-scale groundwater level fields. Such maps can be helpful to organize management scenarios for the sustainability of groundwater resources in large hydrogeological districts and to assess the climate change effect of hydrometeorological variables on the groundwater resources.

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